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Особливості іншомовної підготовки майбутніх учителів технологій

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***Анотація.** Статтю присвячено дослідженню особливостей іншомовної підготовки майбутніх учителів технологій у закладах вищої педагогічної освіти.*

***Метою** дослідження є теоретичне обґрунтування змісту, структури та організаційних засад іншомовної підготовки майбутніх учителів технологій, а також визначення ефективних підходів, методів і форм формування іншомовної професійної компетентності на основі англійської мови.*

***Методи.** У процесі дослідження використано комплекс загальнонаукових і спеціальних методів, зокрема аналіз, синтез, порівняння, узагальнення наукових джерел з проблем іншомовної підготовки педагогічних спеціальностей, системний і компетентнісний підходи, а також теоретичне моделювання структури іншомовної професійної компетентності майбутніх учителів технологій. Методологічну основу дослідження становлять положення сучасної педагогіки, лінгводидактики та теорії професійної освіти.*

***Результати.** У результаті дослідження уточнено сутність поняття*

«іншомовна професійна компетентність майбутнього вчителя технологій» як інтегративної якості особистості, що поєднує лінгвістичний, комунікативний, соціокультурний і професійно-діяльнісний компоненти. Визначено специфіку професійної діяльності вчителя технологій як чинник відбору змісту іншомовної підготовки та обґрунтовано міждисциплінарний характер навчання іноземної мови. Проаналізовано особливості організації іншомовної підготовки, зокрема професійну спрямованість навчального матеріалу, інтеграцію англійської мови з фаховими дисциплінами, формування комунікативних умінь у професійних ситуаціях, використання автентичних фахових текстів, технічної документації та цифрових ресурсів англійською мовою. Встановлено ефективність застосування інтерактивних методів навчання, проєктної діяльності, інформаційно-комунікаційних технологій та самостійної роботи студентів у процесі формування іншомовної професійної компетентності.

Висновки. *Зроблено висновок, що іншомовна підготовка майбутніх учителів технологій має бути системною, професійно орієнтованою та інтегрованою з фаховою підготовкою. Реалізація таких підходів сприяє підвищенню рівня готовності майбутніх педагогів до використання англійської мови у професійній діяльності, професійному саморозвитку та академічній мобільності.*

Ключові слова: *іншомовна підготовка; іншомовна професійна компетентність; майбутні вчителі технологій; професійно орієнтоване навчання; англійська мова; міждисциплінарна інтеграція; інтерактивні методи; педагогічна освіта.*

Features of foreign language training for future technology teachers

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the peculiarities of foreign language training for future technology teachers in higher pedagogical education institutions. The aim of the study is to theoretically substantiate the content, structure and organisational principles of foreign language training for future technology teachers, as well as to identify effective approaches, methods and forms of foreign language professional competence development based on the English language.*

Methods. *The study uses a set of general scientific and special methods, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalisation of scientific sources on the problems of foreign language training for pedagogical specialities, systemic and competence-based approaches, as well as theoretical modelling of the structure of foreign language professional competence of future technology teachers. The methodological basis of the study is formed by the provisions of modern pedagogy, linguodidactics and the theory of professional education.*

Results. *As a result of the study, the essence of the concept of 'foreign language professional competence of future technology teachers' as an integrative quality of personality, combining linguistic, communicative, sociocultural and professional-activity components, has been clarified. The specifics of the professional activity of a technology teacher as a factor in the selection of foreign language training content are identified, and the interdisciplinary nature of foreign language teaching is*

substantiated. The features of foreign language training organisation have been analysed, in particular the professional orientation of teaching materials, the integration of English with professional disciplines, the formation of communication skills in professional situations, and the use of authentic professional texts, technical documentation and digital resources in English. The effectiveness of interactive teaching methods, project activities, information and communication technologies, and independent work by students in the process of developing foreign language professional competence is established.

Conclusions. *It is concluded that foreign language training for future technology teachers should be systematic, professionally oriented and integrated with professional training. The implementation of such approaches contributes to increasing the level of readiness of future teachers to use English in their professional activities, professional self-development and academic mobility.*

Keywords: *foreign language training; foreign language professional competence; future technology teachers; professionally oriented training; English language; interdisciplinary integration; interactive methods; teacher education.*

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks (Introduction). Contemporary transformational processes in the education system, caused by globalisation, digitalisation and Ukraine's integration into the European educational space, highlight the problem of training teaching staff capable of functioning effectively in conditions of intercultural and professional communication. Of particular importance is the foreign language training of future technology teachers, whose professional activities are related to the use of modern technologies, access to international information resources, participation in educational projects and the study of professional literature in foreign languages. At the same time, the practice of training future technology teachers in higher education institutions indicates the existence of contradictions

between the growing requirements for the level of foreign language professional competence and the actual level of development of the relevant skills and abilities in students.

The relevance of the study is determined by the need to rethink the content, forms and methods of foreign language training for future technology teachers in accordance with modern educational standards and labour market needs. Foreign languages in the training of specialists in the technology sector are no longer just a general education discipline but have acquired the status of an important tool for professional development, self-realisation and academic mobility. In this context, special attention should be paid to the professionally oriented nature of foreign language training, its integration with professional disciplines and its focus on the formation of communicative competence in situations typical for future professional activity.

Analysis of recent research and publications (Literature Review). In recent years, the problem of foreign language training of students majoring in pedagogy has gained increasing attention in both national and international scientific discourse. Contemporary studies focus primarily on the formation of foreign language professional competence as an integral component of teacher training, emphasizing its role in professional communication, academic mobility, and lifelong learning [1; 4; 7].

Terletska [11] analyses the historical and methodological foundations of foreign language training for future teachers and argues that traditional grammar-oriented models do not meet the communicative needs of modern pedagogical practice. The author substantiates the necessity of updating teaching approaches towards communicative and competence-based models, although the study does not address profession-specific language needs of teachers of technological disciplines.

Maksymchuk [8] investigates the use of interactive technologies in foreign language education in higher education institutions and demonstrates their positive impact on students' communicative activity and motivation. However, the research is

limited to general pedagogical specialities and does not consider the specifics of subject-oriented professional communication.

Sytnik [10] focuses on the role of linguistic and cultural content in forming foreign language communicative competence of pedagogical students. The study highlights the importance of authentic materials and socio-cultural context but does not examine interdisciplinary integration with professional subjects.

The issue of integrating foreign language training with professional practice is explored by Lipatov and Popova [7], who analyse dual education models and prove that combining language learning with professional activity enhances transversal and intercultural competences. Nevertheless, their research lacks detailed methodological recommendations for language instruction in technological education.

Kravets and Pryimak [6] examine professional competence within the framework of the New Ukrainian School, defining foreign language communication skills as an essential component of teachers' professional readiness. At the same time, the authors focus mainly on foreign language teachers, leaving aside non-linguistic pedagogical specialities.

Zorochkina et al. [4] study the preparation of future primary school teachers for developing pupils' foreign language competence. Their findings confirm the importance of methodological and linguistic training but do not address the professional communication needs of future teachers in technical and technological fields.

Recent Ukrainian studies by Hrynyova and Savchenko [3] emphasize the effectiveness of professionally oriented foreign language instruction in teacher education, while Kozachenko [5] substantiates the pedagogical potential of integrating foreign language learning with technological disciplines. These works highlight the relevance of interdisciplinary approaches but remain mostly theoretical and lack empirical validation.

International research also contributes significantly to understanding foreign

language professional competence. Nation and Macalister [14] consider curriculum design principles for language education and stress the importance of needs analysis in professional contexts. Hamp-Lyons and Heasley [12] focus on academic and professional communication skills in English, underlining the necessity of preparing students for real-life professional tasks. However, these studies do not specifically address teacher training in technological education.

Thus, the analysis of recent research indicates that while foreign language training and professional competence development of future teachers are widely discussed, the issue of foreign language training of future teachers of technologies remains insufficiently explored. In particular, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that combine professional orientation, interdisciplinary integration, and communicative practice based on authentic technological content. Addressing these gaps determines the relevance and novelty of the present research.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Although contemporary scientific literature covers a wide range of issues related to foreign language training, there are significant gaps:

- a lack of research focused specifically on future technology teachers, even though technology education has its own characteristics (professionally oriented terminology, technical communication, specific situations of professional dialogue);
- insufficient empirical research on the effectiveness of specific methods of integrating foreign language training with professional technology disciplines;
- limited attention to measuring the level of foreign language competence specifically in professional situations, which is important for future technology teachers;
- minimal number of publications with qualitative and quantitative data on the impact of interactive and blended language learning on the professional competences of future technology teachers;
- insufficient theoretical specification of the structure of foreign language

professional competence specifically for technology teachers.

An analysis of scientific sources shows that the issue of foreign language training for future teachers is quite widely represented in scientific research, but the issues of foreign language training specifically for future technology teachers are considered fragmentarily and require further theoretical generalisation. The specifics of selecting foreign language teaching content, methods and forms of work that take into account the specifics of the professional activity of technology teachers remain insufficiently researched. This determines the expediency of conducting a comprehensive analysis of the specifics of foreign language training for future technology teachers in modern conditions.

Formulation of the article's objectives. The purpose of this article is to identify and theoretically substantiate the peculiarities of foreign language training for future technology teachers in higher education institutions.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are to be accomplished:

- to analyse scientific approaches to the problem of foreign language training for future teachers;
- to clarify the essence of the concept of foreign language professional competence of future technology teachers;
- to identify the main features of foreign language training for future technology teachers;
- to characterise effective forms and methods of foreign language training, taking into account professional orientation.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the scientific results obtained. In modern pedagogical science, foreign language training is considered an integral part of the professional training of future teachers, aimed at developing the ability to communicate effectively in a foreign language [2; 8]. In this regard, the key result of training is foreign language professional competence, which most researchers define as an integrative characteristic of a personality that combines

language knowledge, communication skills, sociocultural awareness and professionally oriented skills [11; 5].

The structure of foreign language professional competence of future technology teachers includes linguistic, communicative, sociocultural, and professionally-oriented components [8; 6].

In particular, the linguistic component requires proficiency in general and specialised English vocabulary (materials, tools, safety instructions, manufacturing process), as well as grammatical structures characteristic of describing technological processes (passive voice, imperatives) [14; 10].

Thus, the foreign language professional competence of a future technology teacher is applied in nature and is formed taking into account the specifics of pedagogical and technological activities [10; 4].

The professional activity of a technology teacher is related to the study of technological processes, instructional materials, and digital resources, a significant part of which is presented in English [11; 8]. This necessitates the selection of language material focused on the real professional needs of future specialists. Scientific research emphasises that it is advisable to use English-language texts related to the description of technological processes (How a 3D printer works), safety rules (Safety rules in the workshop), and instructions for using equipment (How to operate a CNC machine) [8; 10]. This approach contributes to the development of skills in working with professional information and the formation of skills in its practical application [7; 6].

Foreign language training for future technology teachers is interdisciplinary in nature, as it integrates knowledge of foreign languages, pedagogy and professional technological disciplines [6; 7].

Researchers emphasise that such integration contributes to the formation of holistic professional thinking and increases students' motivation to learn English [10; 9]. The practical implementation of an interdisciplinary approach involves completing

interdisciplinary tasks, analysing English-language materials while studying professional disciplines, and developing projects in English [8; 4].

The professional orientation of foreign language training is considered to be the leading principle of its organisation [11; 8]. The content of English language teaching should reflect the real professional needs of future technology teachers and include topics related to modern technologies, digital tools and educational innovations (Technology in education, Digital tools for teachers) [4; 10]. The integration of foreign language training with professional disciplines ensures that future technology teachers develop the ability to use English as a tool for professional activity [10; 5]. In particular, students can prepare project descriptions in English, analyse English-language video materials on technological topics, and work with technical documentation [8; 9].

The development of communication skills involves creating learning situations that are close to the real professional activities of a technology teacher [7; 7]. These include explaining instructions in English, discussing the results of project activities, and participating in professional discussions on the implementation of innovative technologies [11; 10].

The use of authentic professional materials in English (instructions, video lessons, scientific articles) contributes to the formation of foreign language professional competence and the development of skills in working with real language samples [5; 9].

Interactive teaching methods, project activities, the use of information and communication technologies, and independent work by students are considered effective means of developing foreign language professional competence in future technology teachers [8; 7; 9; 15].

Conclusions. In the course of the study, a theoretical analysis of the problem of foreign language training of future technology teachers in higher pedagogical education institutions was carried out. A summary of the results of the study of

scientific sources showed that foreign language training for modern teachers should be considered not as an auxiliary element of professional education, but as an important factor in the formation of their professional competence and competitiveness in the educational services market.

The study found that foreign language training for future technology teachers is based on a combination of linguistic, communicative and professionally oriented components and is aimed at developing foreign language professional competence as an integrative quality of personality. An important result of the study is the clarification of the structure of foreign language professional competence, which includes linguistic, sociocultural, communicative and professionally-oriented components that ensure the ability of future technology teachers to effectively use English.

Based on the analysis, the main features of foreign language training for future technology teachers have been identified, namely:

- professional orientation of foreign language teaching content, taking into account the specifics of technological and pedagogical activities;
- interdisciplinary nature of foreign language training, which ensures the integration of foreign languages with professional disciplines;
- a focus on developing communication skills in typical professional situations;
- the use of authentic English-language professional materials as a means of bringing the learning process closer to the real conditions of professional activity;
- the use of interactive methods, project activities and information and communication technologies in the process of foreign language training.

The results of the study confirm the expediency of considering English as a tool for the professional development of future technology teachers, which contributes to their readiness to use modern teaching technologies, participate in international educational projects and engage in professional self-development. Prospects for further scientific research are seen in the development and experimental testing of models of foreign language training for future technology teachers, the

creation of professionally oriented teaching and methodological complexes, as well as in the study of the possibilities of using digital educational platforms and online resources for the formation of foreign language professional competence of students of pedagogical specialities.

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